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D3.3

Release 2 of AI-driven inter-domain network control, management, and orchestration innovations

POLITO

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Abstract

This document presents the advancements in the functional design of the AI-driven multi-stakeholder inter-domain control plane (AICP) under the PREDICT-6G framework. This release focuses on extending support for heterogeneous data planes, enabling the integration of multi-technology deterministic domains with seamless interoperability. AICP is empowered by four cornerstone enablers: i) AI/ML for dynamic resource optimization, ii) Digital Twins for predictive service performance and system modelling, iii) Enhanced data management for real-time monitoring and insights, and iv) Cross-domain orchestration for end-to-end lifecycle governance of deterministic services. Additionally, the document explores advanced methodologies to abstract and represent diverse underlying network technologies within the AICP framework, addressing a fundamental requirement for effective E2E service lifecycle management.

Keywords

Network Determinism, Predictability, Reliability, Time-sensitiveness, TSN, DetNet, RAW, Control Plane, Cross-domain, Data and Network modelling, AI/ML

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R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Acronyms and definitions

3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AlaaS	AI-as-a-Service
AICP	AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
DetNet	Deterministic Networking
DoA	Description of Action
DT	Digital Twin / Digital Twinning
E2E	End-to-End
FIFO	First-in First-out
HW	Hardware
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MD	Managed Domain

MDP	Multi-domain Data-Plane
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MS	Management Service
NF	Network Function
OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access
QoS	Quality of Service
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RU	Resource Unit
STA	Wi-Fi Station
SW	Software
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TWT	Target Wake Time
WP	Work Package

Table of partners

Short Name	Partner
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
NOK	Nokia Solutions and Networks KFT
ERC	Ericsson Espana SA
INT	Intel Deutschland GMBH
TID	Telefonica Investigacion y Desarrollo SA
ATOS	ATOS IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL
GES	Gestamp Servicios SA
NXW	Nextworks
COG	Cognitive Innovations Private Company
SIM	Software Imagination & Vision SRL
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
UPC	Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
UNIPD	Universita degli Studi di Padova
IDE	Interdigital Europe LTD

1 Executive Summary

This document outlines the advancements achieved in the AI-driven multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control Plane (AICP) design, forming the backbone of the PREDICT-6G platform. Building on the work outlined in Deliverable D3.2 [D3.2], this release expands on the mechanisms to achieve multi-technology, deterministic service delivery across heterogeneous domains.

The document explores several critical aspects in the design and implementation of the AICP, starting with **architectural advances**, enabling seamless integration of diverse technologies, ensuring interoperability and efficient resource utilization. By incorporating advanced orchestration layers and refined inter-domain interfaces, the architecture is suitable for dynamic environments and multi-stakeholder scenarios. These improvements address the complexities of heterogeneous data planes, strengthening unified control while maintaining adaptability to evolving operational requirements.

In addition, the document focuses on several **technological enablers**. Namely, AI and machine learning are leveraged for intelligent resource allocation and predictive analytics, enabling proactive network management, while Digital Twins provide real-time simulation capabilities, facilitating the prediction and optimization of system performance. Enhanced data collection and management systems ensure continuous monitoring and analysis, providing insights for maintaining service quality. Inter-domain orchestration mechanisms facilitate the seamless coordination of multi-technology and multi-stakeholder environments, ensuring the lifecycle management of end-to-end deterministic services.

Finally, the document provides **operational workflows** to outline the processes essential for the effective implementation and management of the AICP framework. These workflows define the interactions between architectural components and technological enablers, ensuring seamless coordination across diverse network domains.

The key innovations presented in this document are the following:

- Services were specified with the purpose of integrating Digital Twins into the PREDICT-6G architecture and services were provided for AI/ML operations.
- The AICP architecture was revised by regrouping a set of former AI-related Management Services as part of a new MLOps framework exhibiting a cleaner design.

- Enhancements include the scheduling of OFDMA resources leveraging the Target Wake Time (TWT) mechanism for the support of time-sensitive Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) traffic and a reinforcement learning approach.
- Resource reconfigurability has been addressed ensuring that all services meet their performance requirements while optimizing the use of available computational, radio, and energy resources.
- Computation of KPIs of non-TS flows within Digital Twin in the wired TSN domain.
- Introduction of a WiFi Digital Twin for the modelling and simulation of wireless networks with TWT support as well as for multidomain networks including both Wi-Fi and wired domains.
- Update of Operation Workflows according to the last version of the AICP architecture assuming that the computation of the service also relies on digital twinning.

2 Introduction

The demand for deterministic communication services continues to grow, driven by critical applications in industries such as autonomous transportation, industrial automation, and healthcare. These services require strict guarantees on latency, reliability, and predictability, which are often difficult to achieve across heterogeneous network domains. Current solutions face significant challenges in delivering end-to-end deterministic performance due to limitations in interoperability, scalability, and adaptability when spanning diverse technological and administrative boundaries.

This document presents the advancements in the design and operationalization of the AI-driven multi-stakeholder inter-domain control plane (AICP) within the PREDICT-6G project. Building on the foundational principles introduced in D3.1 [D3.1], this release focuses on expanding the architectural, technological, and operational capabilities of the framework to address the complexities of next-generation deterministic networks.

The architectural enhancements of AICP, discussed in Section 3, emphasize modularity and scalability, enabling seamless deployment across various operational contexts. Section 4 elaborates on the key technological enablers driving the system, including AI/ML for predictive resource allocation, Digital Twins for real-time network modelling, advanced data collection for service monitoring, and inter-domain orchestration to support lifecycle management. Section 5 explores the different Digital Twins for the Ethernet and WiFi domains. Section 6 shifts the focus to the representation and abstraction of data planes, tackling challenges in modelling heterogeneous underlying networks to enable effective service management. Section 7 delves into the lifecycle management of deterministic services, presenting strategies to ensure consistent service performance from provisioning to termination. Section 8 outlines the operational workflows that connect these components, detailing processes for seamless service initialization, dynamic adaptation, and efficient inter-domain coordination. Finally, Section 9 lists the contribution of WP3 to the standardization effort of the project.

3 AICP Updates and External Components

3.1 Summary of content from previous deliverables

The AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane (AICP) of the PREDICT-6G reference system architecture has been first reported in Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1] and it has reached its fully developed form in Deliverable D1.2 [D1.2]. The AICP follows a service-based approach with two types of Management Domains (MDs): the End-to-end (E2E) MD with the scope of composing and managing end-to-end deterministic services across multiple domains, and a number of Domain Specific MDs with the scope of providing deterministic services within the boundaries of their own supervised domain. The logical separation of concerns between E2E and Domain Specific scopes enables PREDICT-6G architecture to scale by adapting the implementation of Domain Specific services to new technologies while keeping the E2E services independent from the technical complexity of the underlying physical network.

The latest version of the architecture, reported in D1.2 [D1.2], has explicitly enumerated many services (both on the E2E and domain levels) that may be classified into three categories, illustrated in **Figure 3-1**.

1. First, the services with white (uncoloured) background in **Figure 3-1** are the ones that provide capabilities essential for the multi-domain deterministic service management, which is the core set of PREDICT-6G capabilities. These are essential to be defined in all management domains as they are specific to PREDICT-6G.
2. Second, services were specified with the aim of integrating Digital Twins into the PREDICT-6G architecture (marked by blue background in **Figure 3-1**).
3. Third, services were provided for AI/ML operations (marked by green background in **Figure 3-1**).

Figure 3-1: Illustration of the AICP architecture changes introduced in Deliverable D3.3.

This deliverable provides an update to the AICP in relation to the 2. and 3. categories of services (DT and MLOps), keeping the 1. category intact. The observations and the experience gathered during the work focusing on the design and implementation of the AICP components clarified that 1. category services (core services essential to PREDICT-6G) need no update, however the changes considering the 2. and 3. category services described in the next section has the beneficial impact of simplifying and increasing the flexibility of the PREDICT-6G system.

3.2 AICP updated services

The changes in the 2. and 3. categories of the AICP services, including their motivation and impact, are explained below and illustrated in **Figure 3-2**.

1. Services related to the Digital Twinning are moved outside of the AICP and generalized to support any type of Digital Twin (DT). In Deliverables D3.1 [D3.1] and D1.2 [D1.2], the “DT Predictive Analytics” and “E2E DT Predictive Analytics” services were defining a specific type of DT with a given implementation and functionality with the scope to predict KPIs of hypothetical new traffic flows. However, in the context of PREDICT-6G, DTs are now repositioned as enablers for any of the PREDICT-6G defined core services, with the “DT Predictive Analytics” being just one potential example DT that could be used as a supporting capability during, e.g., deterministic service provisioning, to consider the predicted KPIs on the potential service paths and select the best one for the deterministic flows. This example is illustrated in **Figure 3-2** through the consumption of DT services by the “(E2E) Path Computation” core services. In essence, this re-positioning of the DTs enables to integrate any existing DT with the PREDICT-6G AICP service architecture by making the DTs providing services to the PREDICT-6G AICP core services, or as a direct implementation alternative, use DTs to directly implement (some of) the PREDICT-6G AICP services.
2. Services related to the Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) are likewise moved outside of the AICP, with the same intention as discussed with the DTs. AI is a technology that may be integrated in the implementation of many of the AICP core services, therefore this re-positioning of MLOps as a service to the core AICP management services unlocks the potential for any service to leverage AI to provide their own capabilities. At the same time, the explicit means of how to train or manage AI models is not prescribed as this is specific to the implementation of the services and the MLOps itself. It is quite likely that existing MLOps frameworks will be used to implement and manage AI models for any vendor that implements PREDICT-6G AICP services, therefore the AICP architecture should remain flexible to accommodate any of those without creating unnecessary integration burden on the PREDICT-6G service-based architecture itself. An example for using AI for e2e service automation is illustrated in **Figure 3-2**, which at the same time also proposes that the DT services also utilize MLOps to create AI based DT models. All of this has become possible without having to change the PREDICT-6G AICP core services.

Figure 3-2: Example service-based integration of DTs and MLOps to support the functionality of AICP services.

It is important to note that all MLOps and DT capabilities already reported in Deliverables D3.1 [D3.1] and D1.2 [D1.2], continue to be part of the PREDICT-6G project work, implemented capabilities, and resulting demonstrations. The only change is to reposition their APIs and interfaces from being core AICP services to become supporting functions.

Summarizing the benefits of the AICP update:

1. **Simplification** – only specify what makes PREDICT-6G capable of managing e2e deterministic services, without representing implementation choices to achieve those capabilities.

2. **Increased flexibility and scalability** by enabling integration with a much wider range of DTs, without the impact on AICP services. E.g., if a partner wishes to utilize their existing DT of their network that is already synced to the network (implementing monitoring services) and provide closed-loop automation capabilities, this DT (with some added interface logic) could become the implementation of their management domain without having to formally raise their DT capabilities onto the service-based architecture.
3. **Less formal integration** of supporting technologies (such as MLOps) in favour of practical SW and API integration with already working solutions, which yields working solutions sooner than having to formally specify the supporting functions as part of the AICP service architecture.

4 AI Solutions for Multi-domain Control

4.1 Summary of corresponding D3.1 content

The previous release introduced the foundation of the PREDICT-6G system, focusing on the design and implementation of the AICP. This architecture leveraged core technologies such as AI/ML for intelligent resource management for predictive analytics and advanced orchestration to ensure deterministic and reliable E2E service delivery across diverse technological and administrative domains. The emphasis was placed on creating a unified, service-based architecture capable of integrating heterogeneous networks while abstracting their complexities to manage deterministic services.

This updated release focuses on refining the AICP architecture by regrouping a set of former AI-related Management Services as part of a new MLOps framework exhibiting a cleaner design (Section 4.2). Furthermore, with specific reference to the Wi-Fi technological domain, tailored solutions have been developed for resource management within the PREDICT-6G framework. Enhancements include the scheduling of time (Section 4.3) and frequency (Section 4.4) resources in Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access (OFDMA)-based Wi-Fi networks, with the former leveraging on the Target Wake Time (TWT) mechanism for the support of time-sensitive Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) traffic and the latter on the use of a reinforcement learning approach. Finally, resource reconfigurability has been addressed (Section 4.5) by referring to a generic technological domain and by developing a framework that ensures that all services to be supported therein meet their performance requirements while optimizing the use of available computational, radio, and energy resources.

4.2 MLOps solution for AI support

As specified in Section 3, the new version of the AICP architecture design presented in **Figure 3-2** shows how a set of former AI-related Management Services (green blocks in **Figure 3-1**) have been regrouped as part of a new MLOps framework.

The MLOps framework, which has been placed out of the AICP to offer AI-as-a-Service capabilities to the rest of AICP Management Services, not only comprises the previous AI-based Management Services, but also includes serving capabilities to enable the exchange of AI/ML models or inferences in centralized or distributed environments, through the use of specific of APIs. The serving of AI/ML capabilities to other AICP MS seeks optimizing their own functionalities, adding predictability to ensure a deterministic behaviour across the PREDICT-6G architecture.

Figure 4-1 shows the architecture of the proposed MLOps framework, plotting the expected interactions between the legacy AI-based Management Services, as well as the new interfaces to offer AI-as-a-Service (AlaaS) capabilities to the rest of MD and E2E Management Services of the AICP, as well as to the Digital Twin system architecture block.

Figure 4-1: MLOps framework system architecture.

As explained in Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1], the former PREDICT-6G AICP design relied on a combination of Management Services to allow the serving of AI/ML capabilities, including:

- i) Dataset and AI/ML model repositories and registries, designed to store datasets and AI/ML models and record the metadata for each of the stored items.
- ii) Learning Manager to update the information of the repositories and registries and forward it towards the AI/ML Resource Orchestrator when needed.
- iii) AI/ML Resource Orchestrator to implement AI/ML services according to the Learning Orchestrator instructions.
- iv) MD and E2E Learning Orchestrators, which act as the access point between external Management Services in MD and E2E domains and the rest of AI/ML services, receiving queries from external Management Services, deciding the AI/ML models and dataset needed to address these queries, requesting the creation of AI/ML services to the AI/ML Resource Orchestrators and exposing the outcomes.

As shown in **Figure 4-1**, all these services have been put together following a hierarchical approach to compose the new MLOps framework architecture, keeping all the functionalities, interfaces and expected interactions already described in Deliverable D3.1 – Section 5 [D3.1].

Additionally, specific E2E and MD interfaces have been added at the northbound side of the MLOps framework, in the E2E and MD Learning Orchestrators, to allow the interaction with external AICP Management Services or to MD/E2E Digital Twins. These interfaces will be implemented through specific APIs that will be designed for enabling the exchange of data and the serving of AI/ML models or inferences with other MS, implementing the AlaaS proposed approach.

The proposed MLOps framework architecture will be leveraged in PREDICT-6G architecture to offer AlaaS capabilities to the different Management Services of the AICP as well as to Digital Twins, enabling the use of intelligence in the shape of AI/ML models or inferences for enhancing functionalities related to path computation, resource configuration, etc.

4.3 AI-based control framework: Wi-Fi domain

The timely and reliable communication of WiFi devices that are part of a TSN (e.g., IIoT sensor and actuators in an Industry 4.0 setting) is fundamental to prevent costly interruptions to the production chain, and, therefore, avoid substantial monetary losses. However, the shared nature of the wireless channel could be the source of unacceptable delays, as interference and collisions from concurrent devices may undermine the successful transmission of alert messages. In this section, we show how we can overcome this issue using Target Wake Time (TWT) mechanism. One solution could be to have dedicated wireless channels assigned to

each IIoT device. However, this solution is rarely feasible due to the sheer scale of IIoT networks, which may consist of hundreds, if not thousands, of devices sharing limited spectrum resources. Hence, the only viable possibility is to schedule the utilization of shared spectrum resources accurately.

In such a perspective, TWT is a perfect fit for time-sensitive IIoT.

TWT is a feature introduced in Wi-Fi 6 (IEEE 802.11ax) that allows an AP to schedule when each station (STA) in the network should wake up to transmit and receive data. Such a feature brings several advantages:

- **Energy saving:** IIoT devices may be battery-powered, thus having limited energy capacity. By allowing devices to mostly sleep and wake up only during specific scheduled times to exchange traffic, they can save substantial energy and improve battery life;
- **Channel contention mitigation:** by coordinating wake times, STA can take turns accessing the channel, reducing the likelihood of collisions and contention. This noticeably improves the determinism in the communication, when dealing with safety-critical scenarios, and improves communication latency.

Overall, TWT represents a key enabler for latency-sensitive IIoT networks. However, while it defines how to manage the synchronization mechanism, it does not state when to wake up STA. Hence, this calls for the design of an efficient scheduling mechanism to support

TWT-based spectrum allocation in IEEE 802.11ax IIoT networks. Such a solution should guarantee the respect of deadlines to STA messages while maximizing the energy efficiency of the network. Indeed, a device should not wake up too early to save as much energy as possible, nor too late, to ensure the timely delivery of packets.

For this reason, it is imperative to use a scheduling strategy aware of transmission buffer generation times and deadlines. This behaviour is presented in **Figure 4-2**, which introduces in the top diagram an example of a TWT acceptance and scheduling problem. For a scheduling solution to be feasible, the transmission (black bars) cannot overlap in time, as they would cause channel contention. Instead, they must be scheduled sequentially within the grey bars, which indicate the ranges of transmission that respect the deadlines. If a naive First-in First-out (FIFO) approach is used (middle diagram), only a few transmissions can be scheduled, as other transmissions are cancelled because they miss the deadlines. If instead the optimal strategy for scheduling the highest number of transmissions is used (bottom diagram), more

Figure 4-2: TWT acceptance and scheduling problem.

transmissions can be accommodated (twice in this specific case). Note that both approaches are aware of deadlines, which prevents transmissions that would violate them.

In a classic scenario each STA has to send time-sensitive traffic to the AP which, to avoid non-deterministic delays due to channel contention, employs the TWT mechanism to isolate the STA transmissions in the time domain while trying to schedule the highest amount of traffic. Traffic is sent by a STA in the AP-scheduled TWT Service Period (SP).

During a SP, the scheduled STA makes a single transmission (TX hereafter) of the content of its transmission buffer, which carries time-sensitive traffic generated at the application layer.

A scheduling period, i.e., the time interval between consecutive scheduling decisions, is delimited by beacon frames transmitted periodically every T_b by the AP and includes the TWT scheduling decisions valid until the next beacon transmission. A beacon period is divided into D slots of duration $T_s = \frac{T_b}{D}$. A slot defines the temporal resolution of TWT scheduling, meaning that a TWT window starts at the beginning of a slot and lasts for a discrete number of slots.

Every STA m is associated with a signal quality level l_m , which sets the maximum data rate $\rho_m(l_m)$ that can be reliably used by the STA to exchange traffic, and that varies according to the STA capabilities and the network configuration (e.g., channel bandwidth, MIMO).

The traffic that has to be scheduled by the AP is composed of n TXs. The i -th TX is characterized by:

- i. the source STA m_i ;
- ii. the buffer size b_i , that corresponds to the amount of data that m_i has to transmit to the AP;
- iii. the release time r_i , i.e., the time the buffer generated by an application is ready to be transmitted;
- iv. a hard deadline d_i within which the TX has to be received;
- v. a priority v_i associated with the criticality of the information contained in the i -th TX.

We assume the propagation delay to be negligible, i.e., the TX is received as soon as the sender ends its TX. Once the maximum data rate ρ_m and the byte size of the TX b_i are known, the time duration p_i of every TX can be determined through an analytical expression or experimentally.

Note that, for the sake of simplicity, r_i , p_i , and d_i are all expressed in time slots.

The m -th STA is characterized by a specific transmission power P_m^{tx} . We assume P_m^{tx} to be constant regardless of the adopted data rate. Hence, the per-slot energy consumption of STA m is equal to:

$$E_i^{tx} = P_m^{tx} \cdot T_s$$

when the STA is performing the i -th transmission (TX). Therefore, the TX of transmission time p_i requires an overall energy of $E_i^{tx} \cdot p_i$.

Similarly, when idle, the m -th STA requires P_m^{id} power, thus consuming:

$$E_i^{id} = P_m^{id} \cdot T_s$$

every slot. To avoid waste of energy, before and after the i -th TX, STAs transition from the sleep state to the active state and vice versa. Such transitions are associated with the total energy cost E_i^{onoff} , which may not be convenient in case of very short sleep times when, instead, staying active may save energy.

Ideally, the goal is to find a schedule that can accommodate all the TX requests, while also keeping an eye on the overall energy consumption of the system. However, in the case of several overlapping TXs with similar requirements, scheduling all of them may not be possible.

In such cases, we can reject one or more TXs, e.g., those with the lowest priority, or the longest ones. The choice of which TXs to reject strictly depends on the trade-off between energy consumption and traffic priority. For instance, the scheduling algorithm may choose to discard long, albeit high-priority, TX to reduce energy consumption. These two objectives are weighted by the α coefficient, which sets the relative importance of the two objective components. We consider the decision variable to be as follows:

- $\mathbf{x} = [x_i]$, defined as the transmission acceptance vector, where the generic element x_i is binary and indicates whether the i -th TX is admitted.
- $\mathbf{y} = [y_{ij}]$, defined as the transmission sequence matrix, whose element y_{ij} is binary and takes 1 when the i -th TX is scheduled right before the j -th.
- $\mathbf{z} = [z_i]$, defined as the completion time vector with integer completion time for TXs.

In this formulation, two dummy TXs 0 and $n + 1$ are defined to help in modeling the sequence of transmissions. They take the first and the last position of the sequence and are characterized by release dates, transmission times, and priority equal to 0, while the deadlines are instead equal to the maximum deadline of all TXs.

Table 4-1: Summary of notations

Symbol	Description
$m_i \in \{1, \dots, M\}$	Wi-Fi STA performing the TX i
N	Total number of TXs
l_m	Quality level of the link between AP and STA m
$\rho_m(l_m)$	Maximum data rate for the STA m
τ_i	Time needed to transmit b_i
D	Number of time slots in a beacon frame
T_b	Time interval between consecutive beacon frames
T_s	Slot duration (time granularity)
g_i	Generation time for the TX i
d_i	Aol deadline for for the TX i
p_i	Priority level of the TX i
E_i^{tx}	Energy consumed by m_i in a time slot while transmitting
E_i^{id}	Energy consumed by m_i in a time slot while being idle
E_i^{st}	Energy consumed by m_i when transiting from sleep to transmit (and vice versa)
s_{ij}	Auxiliary parameter, taking 1 if $m_i = m_j$, 0 else
x_i	TXOP admission binary variable
y_{ij}	TXOP sequence binary variable
z_i	TXOP end time variable
e_i	Total energy consumed by m_i for the TX i

Table 4-1 provides a summary of all the notations introduced earlier, offering a clear and concise reference for the key terms and symbols used in the optimization problem.

The TASP optimization problem is formulated as reported in **Figure 4-3**. The cost function (1a) is the weighted sum of the rejection cost and the energy cost over all the requested TXs.

TWT Acceptance and Scheduling Problem (TASP)

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\alpha \cdot \left((1 - x_i) \cdot v_i \right) + (1 - \alpha) e_i x_i \right] \quad (1a)$$

s.t.

$$\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^{n+1} y_{ij} = x_i \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, n \quad (1b)$$

$$\sum_{j=0, j \neq i}^n y_{ji} = x_i \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n+1 \quad (1c)$$

$$z_i + p_j y_{ij} + d_i (y_{ij} - 1) \leq z_j \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, n, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n+1, i \neq j \quad (1d)$$

$$(r_i + p_i) x_i \leq z_i \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n+1 \quad (1e)$$

$$z_i \leq d_i x_i \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, n+1 \quad (1f)$$

$$e_i \leq E_i^{onoff} + p_i E_i^{tx} \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, n+1 \quad (1g)$$

$$e_j \geq y_{ij} (s_{ij} E_j^{id} (z_j - p_j - z_i) + (1 - s_{ij}) E_j^{onoff}) + p_i E_i^{tx} \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, n, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n+1, i \neq j \quad (1h)$$

$$z_0 = 0, z_{n+1} = \max_{i=1, \dots, n} \{d_i\} \leq D \quad (1i)$$

$$x_0 = 1, x_{n+1} = 1 \quad (1j)$$

$$x_i \in \{0, 1\}, y_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, n, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n+1, i \neq j \quad (1k)$$

Figure 4-3 TWT Acceptance and Scheduling Problem

The rejection cost is given by the priority of rejected tasks, while the energy cost is determined by constraints (1g) and (1h). Constraints (1b) and (1c) force each accepted TX to precede and succeed only one other TX. Constraint (1d) ensures that if the i -th TX precedes the j -th, the completion time of the former precedes the one of the latter summed by the transmission time p_j . Instead, if the i -th and j -th TXs are not sequential, $z_j \geq 0$. Note that (1d) ensures the

elimination of cycles in the transmission sequence. Constraint (1e) ensures that the completion time of an accepted TX is not less than the sum of its release date and transmission time. The deadline requirement (1f) dictates that the completion time of an accepted TX cannot exceed its deadline. Related to the energy aspects, (1g) sets the upper limit for the energy consumption of a TX, which is equal to the sum of the energy associated with the activation and deactivation of the radio transceiver, and the energy consumed for the transmission. Conversely, (1h) sets the energy consumption lower bound, which depends on whether the current TX is performed by the same STA that performed the one that precedes (s_{ij}). If the STA is the same, instead of going to sleep and in the active state again, it stays active, saving energy and consuming proportionally to the time between the end of the preceding TX z_i and the beginning of the current one in the $z_j - p_j$ slot. Finally, (1i) and (1j) set x and z for the dummy TXs, while (1k) forces x and y to be binary.

The TASP includes both integer and continuous variables, and one quadratic constraint (1h), therefore it belongs to the MIQCP class, whose problems are known to be NP-hard [Burer 2011].

To evaluate the performance of our approach, we introduced a set of baseline methods for comparison, each representing a distinct heuristic:

- **Shortest First:** Prioritizes tasks based on their duration, scheduling the shortest tasks first. If multiple tasks share the same shortest duration, it applies a series of decision criteria to select among them. These criteria are considered in descending order of importance: first, the task with the earliest TX deadline is chosen; if there are still ties, the task with the highest TX traffic priority is selected; next, if the tasks still remain tied, the task with the smallest TX generation time is preferred; and if ties persist, the final selection is made randomly.
- **Random:** Tasks are scheduled in a completely random order. This provides a naïve benchmark, demonstrating the advantage of more structured approaches.
- **FIFO (First In, First Out):** Tasks are scheduled in the order they are generated. In cases where multiple tasks are associated with the same TX and share the same generation time, FIFO further refines its selection by giving priority to the task with the smaller processing time. If the processing times are also equal, FIFO then selects the task with the highest priority.
- **Optimum:** Task scheduling follows the solution calculated by Gurobi, a well-known numerical optimization solver, this policy is available only when the number of STA is lower or equal to 16, as for higher number of STAs obtaining a solution with Gurobi is not feasible;

- NoTWT:** Refers to a mode in which devices do not synchronize their wake-up times for transmissions, resulting in the absence of any explicit scheduling or coordination between devices. In this context, there is no attempt to optimize the wake-up times to reduce energy consumption or avoid contention on the communication channel. This leads to a situation where devices are free to transmit at any time, often leading to channel contention, where multiple devices may simultaneously attempt to access the same communication channel, causing interference and reducing the overall network efficiency.

Preliminary results were obtained using the *ns-3-twt* simulation tool with a network configuration comprising 16 STAs and 1 AP operating on a 2.4 GHz frequency band. Both the STAs and the AP were configured with a SISO 20 MHz channel and an 800 ns guard interval, evaluated over a single beacon interval of 102.4 ms. **Figure 4-4** and **Figure 4-5** illustrate the mean percentage of missed deadlines and mean duration of the violations normalized over the TX times, respectively. For the Optimum policy, results reveal that violations are more frequent for higher α , this because the policy optimizes the rejection cost rather than the energy consumption. Conversely, under the NoTWT policy, the use of standard Wi-Fi channel access results in a dramatic increase in violations by 2 orders of magnitude, proving that this approach is unfit for time sensitive traffic.

Figure 4-4: Mean percentage of missed deadlines relative to all TXs.

Figure 4-5: Mean duration of the deadline violations relative to the TX durations.

4.4 AI-based resource allocation: Wi-Fi OFDMA slicing

4.4.1 Approach and algorithm

In Predict-6G, a HW and SW framework is used for the implementation of time-aware shaping according to the TSN standard in the Wi-Fi domain. This is achieved through the use of queue scheduling at the OS level (see **Figure 4-7**). In Wi-Fi 802.11ax, OFDMA could be exploited to

dynamically allocate frequency resources at every transmission operation as shown in **Figure 4-6**. In contrast to cellular 3GPP technologies, Wi-Fi does not specify a mechanism to schedule across time and frequency simultaneously. The AI-based resource allocation contribution consists in evaluating a reinforcement learning-based approach to distribute the frequency resources in Wi-Fi.

Figure 4-6: Frequency resource allocation (per TxOp) in 802.11ax (OFDMA).

Figure 4-7: Time-aware shaping (802.1Qbv).

4.4.1.1 Reinforcement Learning approach

In Deliverable D3.2 [D3.2], we showed an implementation of a RL approach that exploits a mathematical model of the network to efficiently compute the gradients that enable the model to learn. This approach however cannot be integrated with a real system as there will be no visibility on how a change to the slicing decisions would affect the target goal.

In this deliverable we have adapted the previous approach to a policy-gradient approach, where the system (network) is a black box, and the loss function is obtained from a sample and evaluate mechanism that compares if the probability of a slicing decision is correlated with a positive reward signal from the system and then use the gradient of the policy model to modify the weights of a neural network. In addition, this RL algorithm has been adapted to estimate a Dirichlet distribution, such that each sample from the distribution results in a complete split of the available resources. The resulting slicing decisions are then quantized to match the number of resource units (RU), i.e., frequency resources, available in the Wi-Fi domain.

The problem to solve is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{\pi} \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \mathbb{E}_{s, a \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T r_0(s_t, a_t) \right] \\ \text{s.t. } & \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \mathbb{E}_{s, a \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T r_i(s_t, a_t) \right] \geq c_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{aligned}$$

where

- π is the policy function making the slicing decisions
- s_t is the system state at timestep $t \in T$
- a_t is the action taken (slicing decision) at timestep t
- $r_0(s_t, a_t)$ is the main objective function to be optimized
- $r_i(s_t, a_t)$ are the m constraint functions
- c_i are the m constraint specifications

The following equation defines the final reward function to be optimized combining both the objective and the constraints as a function of the system state and slicing decisions and parameterized by the vector lambda.

$$r_{\lambda}(s_t, a_t) = r_0(s_t, a_t) + \sum_i \lambda_i (r_i(s_t, a_t) - c_i)$$

where

- λ_i is the Lagrangian multiplier

As the network state cannot be differentiated in the real world (black box), instead of taking the gradient of this function and finding the locations where it equals to zero, we follow a Monte Carlo variant of a policy gradient optimization to find the parameters of a neural network that implements the optimized policy:

$$\theta = \arg \max_{\theta} \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \mathbb{E}_{s, a \sim \pi_{\theta}} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T r_{\lambda}(s_t, a_t) \right]$$

The learning approach consists of two steps: sampling and evaluation. In the sampling phase, a fixed policy is selected to run for a time window during which the system state and reward signals are gathered using a randomly sampled Lagrangian multiplier. In the evaluation phase, the gathered info is used to assess what is the probability given by the policy model of choosing the slicing decisions that were taken. This probability is then combined with the reward signal to reinforce or change the weights of good decisions. Parameter update rule:

for each step of the episode $t = 0, 1, \dots, T - 1$:

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta + \alpha \gamma^t G \nabla \ln \pi(A_t | S_t, \theta)$$

where

α is a learning rate hyper-parameter

γ hyperparameter

G is the reward signal (optionally discounted by γ factor)

A_t is the recorded action taken at timestep t

S_t is the recorded system state at timestep t

4.4.2 Initial evaluation

To validate the algorithm, we have integrated it in a closed loop to a proprietary simulator of Wi-Fi where the algorithm provides the slicing decisions, and the network state and rewards signals are provided to the algorithm. In the test scenario, we have defined three STAs and one AP. For each STA, there is a dedicated application that transmits a data with a constant data rate. The AP then splits the available spectrum into the smallest RU sizes (2 MHz) and aggregates to build a slice according to the decisions of the algorithm. The obtained results are shown in **Figure 4-9** and **Figure 4-8**.

Figure 4-9: Slicing decisions across simulation runs.

Figure 4-8: System state across simulation runs.

Scenario: A single simulation run consists of 100 steps. There are three applications, each sending traffic to different STA using a dedicated slice. The relative application data rates differ by a factor of 1.5, 0.8, and 0.4. Every 100 steps the simulation is restarted and the model parameters updated.

Interpretation of results: In **Figure 4-9**, it can be seen that the model gradually learns to dedicate more resources to Slice 1, which transmits more data, as the model tries to maximize the target objective function. In **Figure 4-8**, the buffer state for each transmitting application

is shown. The number of buffered packets is reduced as more resources are allocated to the slice with more demand.

4.5 Dynamic resource configuration in evolving operational conditions

Modern network services demand efficient management of resources to ensure optimal performance, scalability, and adaptability. This is particularly critical in environments where diverse services, each with unique latency, quality, and resource requirements, operate concurrently. The Resource Configurator emerges as a solution for addressing these challenges. By dynamically configuring and allocating resources, it ensures that all services meet their performance requirements while optimizing the use of available computational, radio, and energy resources. Additionally, we consider that some endpoints, such as robots, can serve as computing points. This introduces the need for a Resource Configurator to be aware of various offloading policies, enabling flexible execution of services across the network. The framework described is designed to support any service in a networked environment, ranging from edge computing to cloud-based applications.

The Resource Configurator operates as a central component using a Multi-Layer Graph (MLG) (see **Figure 4-10**) architecture. The model divides the components of the system into:

1. **Service Classes:** Each service class, referred to as a service π , is defined by three primary parameters: (i) a target latency (L_π), representing the maximum allowable delay between the service and the edge; (ii) a quality factor (Q_π), such as the required minimum accuracy for a given task; and (iii) the service duration (T_π), which indicates how long the service is expected to run. A binary variable (h_π) is assigned to each service to denote whether its constraints are strict (hard) or flexible (soft). Example services include packet delivery, security surveillance, or cleaning tasks.
2. **Functions and configurations:** A function $f \in F_\pi$ is the basic operation that supports the execution of a service. These functions, such as autonomous navigation or object detection, serve as the fundamental building blocks. Services can be modelled as directed graphs, where vertices represent the functions, and edges denote dependencies between them. These dependencies can be bidirectional, indicating that some functions may rely on each other's outputs.

Figure 4-10: High level Multi-Layer Graph representation of the System Model.

Each function can be implemented with different configurations ($c \in C_f$). For instance, an autonomous navigation function might use various sensors configurations (e.g., LiDAR or depth cameras), or a computer vision task could use multiple machine learning (ML) models, each with a different balance of accuracy and resource consumption. The combination of a function with a specific configuration defines a “service function”, denoted as $f_c = (f, c)$.

3. **Data Compression Factor:** Different services can tolerate various levels of data compression, especially for tasks like image processing in computer vision. To represent this, a compression factor ($z_{f_c} \in (0,1]$), is introduced, where $z_{f_c} = 1$ indicates maximum data quality, and quality degrades as the compression factor decreases.
4. **Radio and Computational Resources:** The system utilizes edge server resources, including radio resources (e.g., Radio Blocks) and computational resources (e.g., CPU, GPU, or RAM), to execute service functions. These resources are represented by a set $K = \{1, \dots, K\}$ and a vector $S = [S_1, S_2, \dots, S_K]$, detailing the available quantity of each resource type. The specific resources allocated to a service function are denoted by ($s_{f_c} = [s_{f(c,1)}, s_{f(c,1)}, \dots, s_{f(c,K)}]$) representing the resource allocation for that function.
5. **Offloading Policies:** One key advantage of this system is the ability to offload certain functions, either entirely or partially, for local execution. The system supports a set of offloading policies P , with each function assigned a specific policy (p_{f_c}). For instance, a vision processing task might be executed at the edge using a robust ML model or locally on the end device with a lightweight model.
6. **Battery Consumption:** The end device’s remaining battery level is represented as by $E_{tot} \in [0,1]$, where $E_{tot} = 1$ indicates a fully charged battery. Battery consumption for each function depends on the CPU usage and the offloading policy. The energy consumed by a service function is modelled as:

$$e_{f_c}^p(\mu_{f_c}^p, T_\pi) = \phi_{device} \cdot \mu_{f_c}^p \cdot T_\pi$$

where $\mu_{f_c}^p$ represents the average CPU wake-ups per second for the function, and ϕ_{device} is the energy consumed per CPU wake-up.

7. **Service Quality:** $q_{f_c}^p$, is determined by a quality function $q_{f_c}^p(z_{f_c})$, which depends on the compression level of the input data (z_{f_c}).
8. **Service Latency:** The latency of a function, represented as $l_{f_c}^p$, is calculated using a latency function $l_{f_c}^p(s_{f_c}, z_{f_c})$, which accounts for the compression factor and the hardware resources allocated.

The relationship between resource allocation, compression, latency, and quality is highly complex, influenced by the non-linear behaviours of machine learning models and fluctuating network conditions. Instead of creating a detailed mathematical model for every factor, a data-driven approach is adopted. This method uses regression models to estimate quality and latency, simplifying the problem while maintaining precision.

With the system model established, we now present the problem formulation. Let x_{f_c} be a binary decision variable, where $x_{f_c} = 1$ if configuration c is selected. Two key conditions must be satisfied: (i) if no configuration can be assigned to any function in the set F_π , the service is discarded; and (ii) each function must adhere to exactly one configuration. Beyond selecting a function configuration, the framework also determines the appropriate offloading policy p from the set of available policies P for each service function. A binary decision variable $y_{f_c}^p$ is used, where $y_{f_c}^p = 1$ if policy p is selected. Each service function must conform to a single policy, and if no suitable policy can be chosen, the entire service class will be rejected.

As expected, each service function must satisfy the latency and quality requirements specified by the service. To achieve this, the framework must determine the optimal resources s_{f_c} , compression factor z_{f_c} , function configuration c , and offloading policy p while meeting latency and quality constraints. Since the end device rely on battery power, the predicted energy consumption must not exceed the available battery level. Additionally, the resources allocated to a service function at the edge (S_{f_c}) must not exceed the total available budget of resources (S). This condition is ensured by: S_{f_c} is feasible $\leftrightarrow S_{f_c,i} \leq S_i \forall i = 1, \dots, k \forall f_c \in F_\pi$.

Considering all these constraints, the objective is to select the optimal function configuration, offloading policy, and compression factor for each function to (i) maximize the number of service functions allocated in the system, (ii) minimize resource usage per function at the

edge, and (iii) minimize the end device's energy consumption. This is formalized in the following objective function:

$$\max_{x,y,z} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_\pi} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}_f} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} x_{f_c} y_{f_c}^p (E_{tot} - e_{f_c}^p) - \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i \leq K} \frac{S_{f_c,i}}{S_i}$$

Algorithm 1 Greedy Resource Allocation Algorithm

```

1: Initialization:
2:    $S_{available} \leftarrow S$ ,  $E_{remaining} \leftarrow E_{tot}$ ,  $x \leftarrow 0$ ,  $p \leftarrow 0$ ,
    $S_{edge} \leftarrow 0$ ,  $z \leftarrow 0$ .
3: Priority Score Calculation:
4: for each task  $f \in \mathcal{F}$  do
5:   Compute priority score  $P(f) \leftarrow \frac{U(f)}{MinCost(f)}$ 
6: end for
7: Sort tasks in descending order based on  $P(f)$ 
8: Resource Allocation Loop:
9: for each task  $f$  in  $\mathcal{F}_{sorted}$  do
10:  if  $E_{remaining} \geq e_{edge}(f)$  then
11:     $allocated, S_{edge,f}, z_l \leftarrow GA(f)$ 
12:    if  $allocated$  then
13:       $x(f) \leftarrow 1$  {Accept the task}
14:       $p(f) \leftarrow 1$  {Edge computation}
15:       $S_{edge}(f, :) \leftarrow S_{allocated}$ 
16:       $z(f) \leftarrow z_{allocated}$ 
17:       $S_{available} \leftarrow S_{available} - S_{allocated}$ 
18:       $E_{remaining} \leftarrow E_{remaining} - e_{edge}(f)$ 
19:      Continue to next task
20:    end if
21:  end if
22:  if  $E_{remaining} \geq e_{local}(f)$  and  $a_{local}(f, 1) \geq A(f)$  and
    $l_{local}(f, 0) \leq L(f)$  then
23:     $x(f) \leftarrow 1$  {Accept the task}
24:     $p(f) \leftarrow 2$  {Local computation}
25:     $z(f) \leftarrow 1$  {No compression}
26:     $E_{remaining} \leftarrow E_{remaining} - e_{local}(f)$ 
27:    Continue to next task
28:  end if
29:   $x(f) \leftarrow 0$  {Reject the task}
30: end for

```

Figure 4-11: Greedy Algorithm solver.

transmission latency, optimizing performance for the selected configuration and policy. For simplicity, this implementation assumes a static configuration c and two policies: **Edge Offloading** (edge) and **Local Computation** (local). **Figure 4-11** illustrates the detailed algorithm steps.

The process begins with the initialization of vectors and variables (Step 2). Then, for each service function, the framework calculates the priority score based on Utility Estimation (U_f), and the minimum cost ($MinCost(f)$) required to meet constraints for all feasible policies (Step 5). Functions are then sorted in descending priority order (Step 7). For each function in the

To solve the formulated optimization problem, we propose a **Greedy Resource Allocation Algorithm**. This approach seeks to maximize overall utility by making sequential decisions that prioritize functions providing the highest immediate benefit relative to their resource cost. The algorithm evaluates each service function's potential contribution to the objective and selects configurations and policies that maximize utility while adhering to all constraints. The main steps of the algorithm are: (1) **Priority Calculation:** For each function f_c , calculate a priority score based on the expected utility gain and the minimal resource cost required to meet the service's latency and quality constraints. (2) **Function Sorting:** Arrange functions in descending order of their priority scores to establish the sequence for resource allocation. (3) **Resource Allocation:** Iteratively allocate resources to functions based on priority, ensuring resource limits are not exceeded and constraints are satisfied. (4) **Policy and Configuration Selection:** For each function, choose the optimal policy and configuration to maximize utility while meeting latency, quality, and energy constraints. (5) **Compression Factor Adjustment:** Set the data compression factor z_{f_c} to balance the trade-off between data quality and

sorted list, if the end device's remaining battery is greater than the expected energy consumption for the edge policy, a **Greedy Allocation** function ($GA(f)$) attempts to find a feasible combination of resources and compression factor (Step 11) that satisfies all constraints. If successful, the Boolean variable allocation is set to True. The framework accepts the task (Step 13), selects the **edge policy** (Step 14), stores the allocated resources and compression factor (Steps 15-16), and updates the remaining resources and battery (Steps 17-18). In the second case (Step 22), if the end device's remaining battery is sufficient for the local policy and the quality $A(f)$ and latency $L(f)$ constraints are met, the framework accepts the task (Step 23), sets the policy to local (Step 24), and assigns a compression factor of 1 (Step 25), indicating no data compression since no data is being offloaded. If neither case is feasible, the function is discarded (Step 29), leading to the rejection of the entire service.

The Greedy Algorithm reduces computational complexity by avoiding exhaustive searches, making it suitable for real-time applications. Its straightforward logic facilitates easy implementation and integration into existing systems. By dynamically considering resource availability and constraints, the algorithm adapts to changing system conditions. It is important to note that this algorithm does not guarantee a globally optimal solution, as it focuses on immediate gains rather than long-term benefits. However, it ensures strict adherence to all constraints, making it well-suited for deterministic scenarios. Efficient resource allocation enhances the end device's operational time and improves overall service performance.

In order to evaluate the proposed solution, we develop a score function that verifies whether the selected task meet the defined constraints and computes the overall score, and the number of functions successfully allocated within those constraints. Additionally, it ensures that resource and energy limits are not exceeded. Thus, the solution score is calculated by considering the rewards for accepted task, while deducting the cost associated with resource usage and energy consumption.

Figure 4-12: Evaluation of the proposed framework.

Figure 4-12 compares three strategies for task allocation: **Greedy Resource Configurator**, **Always Offloading**, and **Always Local**, in terms of average performance over 100 trials across varying numbers of functions. The **Greedy Semantic Orchestrator** consistently outperforms the other strategies, showing its adaptability in balancing utility, resource constraints, and energy consumption. **Always Offloading** performs well for smaller numbers of functions but decays as edge resources become saturated. In contrast, **Always Local** exhibits steady but lower performance due to limited computational capacity, highlighting the trade-offs of purely local computation.

5 Digital Twin

5.1 Summary of corresponding D3.1 content

The DT predicts the QoS KPIs of a new service request on a candidate path on a single technological domain, as well as the impact on the QoS KPIs to already provisioned services. Furthermore, the DT predicts the E2E QoS KPIs of a new service request crossing several technological domains. Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1] described the MSs related to the digital twinning in the AICP, introducing both per-domain and E2E DT Predictive Analytics services along with their exposed functionalities. In this deliverable, we first provide an overview of the DT to compute the KPIs of non-TS flows within the wired TSN domain. Then, we address network partitioning and emulation, which generates metrics that are afterwards used for KPIs computation. Finally, we introduce *ns-3-twt*, a simulator built on the well-known ns-3 tool, for

the modelling and simulation of wireless networks with TWT support as well as for multidomain networks including both Wi-Fi and wired domains.

5.2 Network digital twin for the Ethernet TSN domain

TSN consists of a set of standards defined by the IEEE 802.1 working group, which includes the 802.1Qbv time-aware scheduler (TAS). TAS works according to a predefined and static Gate Control List of fixed length that specifies when queues are in open and closed states. The scheduler needs to be defined in a way that *Time-Sensitive (TS) flows* meet the required QoS defined in terms of Key Performance Indicators (KPI), such as E2E delay and delay variation (jitter).

5.2.1 DT overview

An DT is used to estimate the KPIs of requested and already deployed non-TS flows. To simplify KPI estimation, a *partition* of the complete network is defined, created as the union of the path(s) selected for the requested flow(s). The DT emulates such network partition to estimate metrics and compute KPIs of requested and already established non-TS flows. The DT considers the resources allocated to TS flows and propagates synthetically generated traffic targeting.

Network emulation entails the deployment of a scenario defined by means of a set of nodes and a set of links. Nodes consists of: *i)* input *ports (inport)* that receive traffic from other nodes; *ii)* output ports (*outport*) that forward traffic to other nodes; and *iii)* forwarding rules that map flows from inports to outports according to flow routes. Links connect an outport in one node to an inport in a neighbouring node and include parameters such as transmission delay.

Three main types of nodes are considered, namely, *generators*, *switches*, and *sinks*. A *generator* is a type of node that produces synthetic traffic for a flow in the form of arrays of bitrate values (in b/s). In the case of TS flows, traffic generation is based on the flow periodicity, so the generator generates traffic only in those time intervals. As for the non-TS flows, traffic is generated according to probability distributions that characterize inter-arrival burst and packet time and burst and packet size of the service mix characterizing the flow. Traffic is generated with a pre-defined resolution κ . Generators have just one outport that limits traffic generation to a maximum bitrate for traffic shaping purposes. On the other end, *Sink* nodes include a number of inports that serve as end points for each flow terminating at that node.

A *switch* is a node that represents a network device with flow switching capabilities (Ethernet switching is assumed). Outports in switch nodes implement the models and algorithms needed to accurately emulate the capabilities and performance of TS and non-TS capable

interfaces. Specifically, time-aware *flow queue models* are used to emulate TS-capable interfaces. The queue model is defined as eq. (1), where $q(\cdot)$ is the queue state defined as the number of bytes in the buffer, $x(\cdot)$ is the actual input flow received, $y(\cdot)$ is the output flow leaving the queue, and $\mu(t)$ is the time-aware service rate.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(q(t)) = q'(t) = x(q(t), t) - y(q(t), \mu(t)) \quad (1)$$

In brief, network emulation consists in propagating traffic flows from generators to sinks, traversing switches. Such traffic propagation results in metrics, such as queued traffic in every queue of the outputs, that are afterwards used to compute per-flow KPIs, such as e2e delay. The DT estimates two types of KPIs: *i)* *e2e* KPIs, which are provided for non-TS requests only; and *ii)* KPIs *variations* (Δ) computed on the network partition defined by the paths of the flows in the request, for the already deployed non-TS flows if the new flows were finally deployed.

In addition to the queue models and components, the DT includes two databases (DB) that are conveniently updated during network operation: *i)* the *network DB* stores the current status of the network topology (active nodes and links), as well as the details of the already deployed flows; and *ii)* a *monitoring DB* with real e2e performance measurements (delay, throughput, and others) of the existing flows. It is worth mentioning that the availability of fine grain, segmented measurements is of paramount importance for the accuracy of KPI estimations produced by the DT, as well as for QoS monitoring for service assurance guarantees. In this regard, techniques such as in-band network telemetry can be adopted to obtain precise measurements with reduced impact on effective throughput and switching/routing performance.

Figure 5-1 summarizes the main procedure executed by the DT during an iteration of the provisioning process of a service request. The first step consists in computing the network partition (G) and selecting the existing flows (F) from the internal network DB (step 1 in **Figure 5-1**). Then, traffic generators are built and configured to generate traffic according to the specifications in F' (including the requested flows) (2), and queues are configured to emulate the network partition $G'(2')$. The outputs of both processes are used to compose a set of *stages* concatenating generators, switches, and sinks (3). The propagation of the generated traffic through the stages (4) creates a set of metrics that, jointly with the available monitoring data of the existing flows, are used to estimate the KPIs (5) that are finally returned.

Figure 5-1: DT main procedure.

5.2.2 Network modelling and emulation

Figure 5-1 (a) shows an example of the network partition created in the DT for evaluating the provisioning request of TS-2. In this example, all established flows share, at least, one interface with the request, so all of them are included in the emulation. However, those links that are not in the path of TS-2 are excluded from the partition, e.g., links AP2-SW1 and R1-SW1. The figure also shows the different stages that are defined and concatenated to propagate the traffic flows from generators to sinks. Let S be the set of stages, $S(i, j)$ be node j in stage i , and $S(i, j, p)$ be port p (inport or outport) in $S(i, j)$. The connection between nodes in two consecutive stages is performed at the port level if they are connected by a link in the network, e.g., ports $S(i, j, p)$ with $S(i+1, j', p')$. Note that nodes in each stage can be independently evaluated, which enables parallel execution.

Figure 5-2: Example of network partition (a) and detail of SW1 (b).

Algorithm 5-1: Node Propagation

INPUT: S, i, j
OUTPUT: S

- 1: **if** $S(i, j).type = \text{"generator"}$ **then**
- 2: $y \leftarrow \text{generate}(S(i, j))$
- 3: $p \leftarrow S(i, j).outPort$
- 4: $S(i', j'; p) \leftarrow \text{get_neighbor}(S(i, j), p)$
- 5: $\text{add_input_traffic}(S(i', j'; p), y)$
- 6: **else if** $S(i, j).type = \text{"switch"}$ **then**
- 7: $X_{TS}, X_{non-TS} \leftarrow \text{split_input_traffic}(S(i, j))$
- 8: **for** p in $S(i, j).outPorts$ **do**
- 9: $X'_{TS}, X'_{non-TS} \leftarrow \text{in_out_mapping}(X_{TS}, X_{non-TS}, p)$
- 10: $p, \mu \leftarrow \text{reserve_time_slots}(X'_{TS})$
- 11: **for** $p: 0..7$ **do**
- 12: $x \leftarrow \text{select_priority}(X'_{TS}, p)$
- 13: $y \leftarrow \text{propagate}(p, x)$ (eq. (1))

```

14:   <i',j',p'> ← get_neighbor(S(i,j,p))
15:   add_input_traffic(S(i',j',p'), y)
16:   ρ,μ ← update(ρ,μ, y) (eq. (2))
17: return S

```

Algorithm 5-1 shows the process to propagate flows through a given node. It receives the set of stages and the index of a particular node to evaluate and returns the set S updated with metrics such as queued traffic in the outports. The algorithm executes different actions if the node is a generator (lines 1-5 in **Algorithm**) or a switch (lines 6-16), while no propagation is performed in case of a sink node. In case of a generator, synthetic traffic (represented by vector y) is produced with m values generated with the pre-configured resolution κ (line 2), where κ is represented by the duration τ_e of each time slot in the link in the network partition and m equals the number of slots in the related SF_e (line 2). Note that τ_e is limited by the precision of clock synchronization.

The traffic is then injected into the neighbor inport (lines 3-5) ready to be processed in the next stage. In case of a switch, the traffic of the flows entering the node is separated into TS and non-TS (line 7). Then, the following steps are performed for every outport (lines 8-16): *i*) the subset of input traffic flows mapped to that outport is selected (line 9); *ii*) the entire capacity of the port (i.e., service rate μ) is reserved at the beginning of the SF with a duration of the aggregated time windows allocated to TS flows (line 10). $\mu(t)$ is a vector of length m and μ_{max} is defined as the nominal bitrate of the port; and *iii*) non-TS flows are sequentially processed in decreasing priority (lines 11-16). Given a priority pr , the aggregated traffic x belonging to such priority is selected (line 12) and propagated through the queue (line 13) according to the fluid flow model presented in eq. (1). The resultant traffic y is added to the neighboring port (line 14-15). Before processing traffic of the next priority, service rate μ is updated by subtracting the capacity y used by the current priority (eq. (2)) (line 16). The updated set of stages is eventually returned (line 17).

$$\mu(t) = \max(0, \mu(t) - y(t)), \forall t = 1..m \quad (2)$$

Figure 5-1 (b) illustrates the node propagation process for the traffic flows propagated through node SW1. Flows are received through 3 different inports and are forwarded to a common outport; the details of the propagation are shown as an inset in **Figure 5-1 (b)**: *i*) x_{TS-1} and x_{TS-2} reserve a time window of enough duration at the starting of the SF interval; *ii*) the remaining capacity is then used to serve traffic flows x_{QoS-1} and x_{QoS-2} because of their higher priority; and *iii*) the output of the higher priority flows is used to reduce the service rate that remain available for serving low-priority traffic flow x_{BE} .

Algorithm 5-1: KPIs computation

INPUT: S, DB
OUTPUT: KPI

```

1:  $F_{non-TS} \leftarrow \text{get\_nonTS\_flows}(S)$ 
2:  $KPI \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3: for  $f$  in  $F_{non-TS}$  do
4:    $d \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5:   for  $S(i, j, p)$  in  $\text{get\_path}(S, f)$  do
6:      $d \leftarrow d + S(i, j, p).d_e + S(i, j, p).d_q$  (eqs. (3)-(5))
7:     if  $S(i, j).type = \text{"sink"}$  then  $thr \leftarrow S(i, j).x$ 
8:     if  $f.eval\_type = \text{"inc"}$  then  $d \leftarrow d - \text{get\_delay}(DB, f)$ 
9:      $KPI[f][\text{"delay"}] \leftarrow \{\text{"avg": avg}(d), \text{"max": max}(d)\}$ 
10:     $KPI[f][\text{"thruput"}] \leftarrow \{\text{"avg": avg}(thr), \text{"max": max}(thr)\}$ 
11: return  $KPI$ 

```

5.2.3 KPI computation

The result of the node propagation process through the stages and nodes generates metrics that are stored in S . Among the different metrics, we consider the following ones for every stage and node, and for every time $t=1..m$:

- the traffic $x(t)$ received per flow at every inport and the traffic $y(t)$ sent per flow through every outport.
- the constant transmission delay d_e collected at every inport.
- the queueing delay $d_q(t)$ caused by traffic buffering at every outport that depends on the service rate among others.

The proposed DT is based on flow propagation and, therefore, no per-packet metrics are available. To overcome this issue, we propose eq. (3) to estimate d_q as the sum of two time-components: *i)* t_w represents the waiting time due to service rate reservation for TS flows and computed as eq. (4), where function $next$ returns the next time to t where service rate is non-zero; and *ii)* t_q is the estimated time to empty the current buffer $q(t)$ at service rate $\mu(t)$, computed as eq. (5). For the sake of simplicity, we assume that the queue is emptied at the speed of the current service rate when the latter is non-zero and at a constant average value μ_{avg} computed for the whole emulated time when the current service rate is zero.

$$d_q(t) = t_w(\mu(t)) + t_q(q(t), \mu(t)) \quad \forall t = 1..m \quad (3)$$

$$t_w(\mu(t)) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \mu(t) > 0 \\ t' - t & \text{if } \mu(t) = 0, t' = \text{next}(\mu(t') > 0) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$t_q(q(t), \mu(t)) = \begin{cases} 8 \cdot \frac{q(t)}{\mu(t)} & \text{if } \mu(t) > 0 \\ 8 \cdot \frac{q(t)}{\mu_{avg}} & \text{if } \mu(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Algorithm 5-1 presents the pseudocode of the algorithm to compute e2e and incremental KPIs. It starts by selecting the non-TS flows and initializing the KPIs to return (lines 1-2 in **Algorithm 5-1**). Then, the path of each flow is retrieved and the e2e delay d is computed as the sum of d_e and d_q components, element-wise for every time t , for all the ports in the path (lines 3-6). When reaching its sink node, flow input traffic is stored as throughput (*thruput*) (line 7). In case of incremental evaluation, the delay monitored in the segments of the evaluated path is retrieved from the monitoring DB and used to recompute the estimated e2e delay as the variation w.r.t. the monitored one (line 8). Finally, the KPIs (delay and throughput) for every flow are stored (lines 9-10). Note that the aforementioned process generates values for every time t reproduced in the emulation. To facilitate performance evaluation analysis and further decision making, the detailed values are summarized in average and maximum statistics and returned as KPIs (line 11).

5.3 TWT simulation-based multidomain DT

TSN has attracted significant attention in recent years, yet there remains a lack of open frameworks for reliably simulating these networks, particularly for realistic simulations of IEEE 802.11ax with the TWT feature. To address this, we introduced *ns-3-twt*, an open tool built on the well-known ns-3 simulator, aimed at simulating wireless networks with TWT support.

Figure 5-3: Architecture of a Digital Twin (DT) of a TSN multi-domain network with TWT.

The simulator, which serves as a DT of a TSN network, has been built upon the advanced ns-3 Wi-Fi TWT simulator outlined in [Venkateswaran 2024]. It provides partial simulation capabilities for the TWT functionality. Specifically, it currently incorporates a subset of TWT agreements, notably the implicit and individual agreements. **Figure 5-3** shows the implemented architecture of the DT for a TSN multi-domain network with TWT.

ns-3-twt has enhanced existing ns-3-based simulators for TWT with the following additional features:

- i. Flexible timing configuration for each transmission, including TWT Service Period (SP) start time and TWT SP duration.
- ii. Deadline support, Age of Information (AoI) deadlines can be set as parameters, allowing logs to record whether these deadlines have been met.
- iii. New helpers and applications to support IEEE 802.11ax simulations with TWT scheduling functionalities.
- iv. Support for multiple STA classes, each customizable with specific parameters like the energy model, distance from the AP, traffic type, uplink/downlink configuration, channel width, and MIMO configuration (up to 4x4).
- v. MCS and SRN logging at the application layer, retired from the MAC and PHY models for each received packet.
- vi. Transparent logging through a new Report Manager module that allows seamless logging of latency and other metrics.
- vii. Support for multiple TWT networks, linked together through a L3 switch and configurable wired links.

In our setup, the AP unilaterally sends Accept frame to all STAs based on a predefined TWT schedule, which coordinates their awake and sleep periods.

A key element in these frames is the "next TWT" field, which specifies the time after the start of the next Beacon Interval when the STA can wake up and access the physical channel within its TWT window. This window remains open for a defined period, referred to as the TWT SP duration. Notably, TWT windows operate on a periodic basis, meaning that unless the AP provides a new schedule, the STAs will continue to use the same TWT windows during each beacon interval.

Figure 5-4 visually illustrates this concept, highlighting the key parameters involved, such as the Beacon Interval, the "next TWT" field, and the duration of the TWT window.

Figure 5-4: TWT window parameters in *ns-3-twt*

BT = Buffer Transmission

Figure 5-5: Simulated TWT application example.

Figure 5-5 presents an illustrative example of a potential TWT application using *ns-3-twt*. The scenario features three STAs, each with a Buffer Transmission (BT), and one AP. It highlights key parameters, such as the traffic generation times (r_i), the TWT window start times (t_i), and the corresponding durations for each STA, all within a single beacon interval.

5.3.1 Dataset for ML model training

As described in Section 4.3, we adopted a ML learning approach leveraging the random forest algorithm, dynamically determines the optimal traffic scheduling policy based on the system's state. This ensures that all traffic is transmitted within the required deadlines.

To construct a robust and comprehensive training dataset, we considered four distinct scenarios with varying numbers of IIoT sensors: 8, 16, 32, and 64. The dataset generation process was structured into three key steps:

1. **Generation of problem instances:** For each scenario we created 500 problem instances.

2. **Generation of solutions:** Using the baselines outlined in Section 4.3, we computed solution for each problem instance.
3. **Performance evaluation:** Each solution was simulated within the *ns-3-twt* environment to evaluate its actual performances. Key metrics analyzed included the number of deadlines met, delays relative to requested deadlines, and the total energy consumed by the STAs.

The generated CSV file containing the scheduling solutions serves as the input to the *ns-3-twt* simulator. Each line in this CSV file represents a unique combination of problem instance and scheduling policy. The line specifies the scheduling parameters, including traffic generation times, TWT window start times, corresponding durations, deadlines, payload sizes, and sensor classes for each STA.

Once the simulator parses each line, it processes the scheduling solution and produces an output CSV file containing detailed performance metrics. This output file includes:

- The policy considered for the scheduling
- The number of STAs in the scenario
- The number of jobs accepted (scheduled)
- The payload size and Modulation and Coding Schema (MCS) used for each STA
- The number of deadlines met during the simulation
- The minimum, maximum, average and variance of the delay across all STAs
- The average and variance of the total energy consumption, both for all the STAs and specifically for the accepted jobs
- The problem instance with scheduling parameters for each STA, as described in input

The simulation setting used for the *ns-3-twt* simulator are presented in **Table 5-1**.

Table 5-1: ns-3-twt simulation settings.

Number of STAs	8-16-32-64	Ack sequence type	AGGR-MU-BAR
Number of AP	1	Number of antennas	1 for each STA and 1 for AP
Frequency	2.4 GHz	Traffic type	Uplink UDP
Channel configuration	SISO 20 MHz channel	Beacon interval simulated	1
Guard interval	800ns		

6 Data Collection and Management

6.1 Summary of corresponding D3.1 content

To guarantee the determinism of a provisioned service, it's important to keep track of QoS and traffic characteristics of the network during the service lifecycle in order to intervene on the network configuration in case of some deviation of those characteristics from the desired values. In this regard, the Data Collection and Management is the AICP component in charge to continuously gather KPIs and other useful data that can be used by DT and MLOps to predict the future behaviour of the network and take decisions accordingly. The scope and the functionalities of the Data Collection and Management component were first introduced in Section 6 of Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1] and did not undergo any changes: two MSs of the AICP architecture, one local to the technological domain (Measurement Collection) and one at the E2E level (E2E Monitoring), perform the collection and the normalization of meaningful data into a common format. The data collected at the local domains are technology specific since the source is the Data Plane; the data collected at the E2E domain are nothing but the ones collected by the Measurement Collection of the local MDs, furtherly abstracted and properly organized to let the automatic management of the E2E services. The access to the data is then controlled by some Authentication and Authorization mechanisms to guarantee a differentiated access on a data consumer basis and at different granularity. The overall set of functionalities exposed by the two MSs is the same and summarized as follows:

- **Historical data management:** to store data in form of timeseries.
- **Real-time data management:** to expose data in a near real-time fashion.
- **Data Manipulation:** to allow service consumers to compute data aggregation statistical functions.
- **Service Configuration:** to dynamically configure data sources as well as manage data consumers.

6.2 Data Unit Groups-Enabled DetNet Domains

The DUG-enabled DetNet router [DUG, 2024] offers PREOF functionality, as described in Deliverable D2.3 [D2.3] in further detail, and its integration with PREDICT-6G's AICP follows a standard-compliant realisation with the particular focus on IRTF's DT draft [RTF NDT, 2024]. This section describes the DT-centric AICP and the necessary domain-specific MSs to integrate the DUG-enabled DetNet router. While Section 6.2.1 provides the architectural overview of the

MSs realised for the Location and Sensing use case (within which the DUG-enabled DetNet router is integrated and validated in), Section 6.2.2 provides the description of the finalised Data Collection Function (DCF) for monitoring purposes.

6.2.1 End-to-End and Domain-Specific Control Plane Integration

For the realisation of the AICP in the Localisation and Sensing use case, **Figure 6-1** illustrates the chosen MSs of the DT as well as the domain-specific MSs.

Figure 6-1: E2E and Domain-Specific Control Plane Integration for DUG-Enabled DetNet Routers.

As depicted in **Figure 6-1**, the following AICP (DT) Network Functions (NFs) are realised for the DUG-enabled DetNet router:

- **Topology Management Function (TMF):** This MS manages topology-related information from each domain (DetNet router IDs, port IDs and link IDs between ports of routers). Furthermore, the TMF also receives properties (capabilities) of DetNet routers and their ports. The Ntmf interface of the TMF allows routers to register with the TMF.
- **Data Monitoring Function (DMF):** This MS collects and stores network monitoring information about the routers, ports and links reported to the TMF by a domain. The Ndmf interface allows DetNet routers to register with the DMF.
- **Path Computation Function (PCF):** This MS administers the network paths of service flows across the routing fabric, which is composed of DetNet routers, their ports and links. The Npcf interface allows to create, modify or delete a service flow network path.

The DetNet-enabled 3GPP domain implements the following domain-specific NFs:

- Time Sensitive Communication and Time Synchronization Function (TSCTS): This 3GPP-compliant NF allows external applications (acting as an AF, e.g. the DT) to interact with a 3GPP system that acts as a DetNet router.
- Data Collection Function (DCF): This domain-specific NF allows the DT (AICP) to retrieve monitoring information from the DetNet-enabled 3GPP domain, enabling the DT to administer service flows in an end-to-end fashion.

6.2.2 Data Collection Function

This section describes the implementation of the DCF NF of the DUG-enabled DetNet router for the Localisation and Sensing use case. **Figure 6-2** illustrates the monitoring implementation of the DUG-enabled DetNet router. The implementation is composed of the collection of monitoring data inside the DetNet router, a monitoring agent to retrieve that information and writing the aggregated information in a time-series format to a database.

Figure 6-2: Software design of the DUG-enabled DetNet router and DCF for monitoring purposes.

As described in D2.3 [D2.3], the DUG-enabled DetNet router is implemented using eBPF and operates in kernel (XDP) and user space (AF_XDP), with most monitoring-related information being determined in the kernel space. eBPF programs lack access to persistent memory storage within their program context, which poses a challenge for collecting monitoring information in a given time interval. eBPF programs can access BPF maps through auxiliary

methods exposed by the kernel, allowing the temporary storage of information. BPF maps are referenced within the eBPF code and are defined upon loading an eBPF application (both XDP and AF_XDP). BPF maps offer key/value storage capabilities and allow to monitor BPF information per CPU or across all CPUs. They can be shared between user space and separate eBPF programs that are operating at different locations inside the kernel. The interlinkage between XDP and AF_XDP using BPF maps is shown in **Figure 6-2**.

There are several types of BPF maps, including hash maps, array maps, Least Recently Used (LRU) hash maps. The list of maps used in the program are:

- **BPF_MAP_TYPE_XSKMAP**: This is used along with the `bpf_redirect_map` [eBPF, 2024] helper to redirect traffic to userspace, bypassing the kernel network stack. It is an array style map, where the indices go from 0 to `max_entries-1`. The values of this map are the file descriptor of specially prepared network socket.
- **BPF_MAP_TYPE_HASH**: This is a generic map type with no restrictions on the structure of the key and value. Hash-maps are implemented using a hash table, allowing for lookups with arbitrary keys.

Common operations on BPF maps include `bpf_map_update_elem`, `bpf_map_lookup_elem`, and `bpf_map_delete_elem`, `bpf_redirect_map`. Maps have multiple functions, including acting as a global coordination tool also acting as a communication channel between userspace and kernel eBPF programs.

The **BPF_MAP_LOOKUP_ELEM** command is used to lookup a single value in a map. This command will return 0 on success or an error number (negative integer) on failure [eBPF, 2024].

The **BPF_REDIRECT_MAP** redirects the packet to the endpoint referenced by *map* at index *key*. *It returns* XDP_REDIRECT on success.

The **BPF_MAP_UPDATE_ELEM** command is used to insert or update a single value in a map. This command will return 0 on success or an error number (negative integer) on failure [eBPF, 2024].

The helper `bpf_trace_printk()` is the BPF counterpart of `printf()`. Monitoring BPF applications is made much easier with the help of `bpf_trace_printk()`, or more accurately, the `bpf_printk()` wrapper. With the help of the `trace_pipe` file, you may view and dump a great deal of helpful data from the BPF side of your BPF application. A basic kernel feature that allows `printf()` to be sent to the standard `trace_pipe` (`/sys/kernel/debug/tracing/trace_pipe`). With three arguments maximum, one percent only, and globally shared `trace_pipe`, this works well for brief examples [eBPF, 2024].

BPF maps is used to store monitoring data like Data unit Group count, flow label count, packets within and outside the cycle time count and the overall packet counts using the map BPF_MAP_TYPE_HASH with the help of the operation BPF_MAP_LOOKUP_ELEM. To print the monitoring data, the bpf_trace_printk function is used, which outputs formatted strings to the kernel's trace buffer. Additionally, with AF_XDP which is a user space application to which packets are redirect with the help of the map BPF_MAP_TYPE_XSKMAP and the operation BPF_REDIRECT_MAP, the BPF map from user space can be updated using the operation BPF_MAP_UPDATE_ELEM, after the packets are processed and transmitted, allowing for more flexible and efficient data handling. This setup enables efficient monitoring of network traffic using eBPF, XDP, and AF_XDP programs.

And example of data written to tracepipe is provided below, which depicts the data points IPv6 packet counts with a DUG header (pcktcnt) and the number of packets outside the configured TSN cycle.

```
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485648.982946: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 0 ipv6_pcktcnt 1
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485649.157987: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 0 ipv6_pcktcnt 2
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485654.437655: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 1 ipv6_pcktcnt 3
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485659.592613: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 0 ipv6_pcktcnt 4
<idle>-0 [001] ..s2. 485659.601379: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 1 ipv6_flwcnt 1 ipv6_pcktcnt 5
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485660.843625: bpf_trace_printk: packet count outside cycle: 1
<idle>-0 [001] ..s2. 485660.852391: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 1 ipv6_flwcnt 1 ipv6_pcktcnt 7
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485661.908846: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 0 ipv6_pcktcnt 8
<idle>-0 [001] ..s2. 485661.925426: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 1 ipv6_flwcnt 1 ipv6_pcktcnt 9
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485662.845523: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 0 ipv6_pcktcnt 10
<idle>-0 [001] ..s2. 485662.854332: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 1 ipv6_flwcnt 1 ipv6_pcktcnt 11
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485663.178192: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 1 ipv6_pcktcnt 12
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485663.971567: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 0 ipv6_pcktcnt 13
<idle>-0 [001] ..s2. 485663.980387: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 1 ipv6_flwcnt 1 ipv6_pcktcnt 14
<idle>-0 [002] ..s2. 485665.632661: bpf_trace_printk: DUG count 0 ipv6_flwcnt 0 ipv6_pcktcnt 15
```

7 Inter-domain Orchestration and Network Control

7.1 Summary of corresponding D3.1 content

Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1] described how PREDICT-6G AICP architecture relies on a hierarchical approach composed of an E2E Management Framework and several technology specific Management Frameworks for controlling different technology domains (3GPP, Wi-Fi, IP, etc.) as presented in Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1]. As part of this design, Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1] – Section 7 introduced a set of frictionless inter-domain orchestration capabilities in the AICP through a set of MSs in both E2E and MDs.

All MSs described in Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1] are still considered as part of the AICP architecture definition in the present document (see **Figure 7-1**). This section recovers a brief description of the complete list of MD and E2E Management Services, setting the ground for the reader to understand the update of the operational workflows described in Section 8. Detailed information about all Management Services as well as details about their early implementation can be found in Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1] – Section 7 and Deliverable D3.2 [D3.2] – Section 4.

Figure 7-1: AICP Management Services related to Inter-domain orchestration and network control.

Management Domain Management Services (MD MS)

- Time Sync:** Management Service used to gather and expose information related to the time sync capabilities and the actual time sync status of the underlying Technology Domain. The time sync information is exposed to the Time Sync Management Service, located in the E2E domain.
- Service Exposure:** Management Service designed to expose information about the current status of the services provisioned in a specific Technology Domain. The service information can be exposed to different types of consumers, e.g. external users, applications or other MSs.

- **Service Automation:** Management Service conceived to ensure the closed-loop automation of a deterministic service in a specific technology domain after the acceptance of a specific E2E service request performed at the E2E domain. Closed-loop automation phases include service provisioning, assurance, and decommissioning, requiring interactions with E2E Service Automation, Path Computation, Resource Configurator, and DTs.
- **Path Computation:** Management Service designed to calculate, compute, and select the most optimal route over a specific technology domain. To perform these actions, Path Computation MS leverages the information related to the topology, the data plane resources availability as well as their deterministic capabilities. The PC MS can also rely on some external entity, such as a Digital Twin for enhanced path computation, if available. Once the path has been calculated, the PC MS forwards it to the Service Automation MS.
- **Resource Configurator:** Management Service used to translate service requirements into a specific resource configuration in the underlying technology domain as part of the service lifecycle management process. To do this, the interaction with the Service Automation MS is required for receiving service requirements and return the selected resource configuration.
- **Topology, Capability and Resource Exposure:** Management Services used to expose topology, deterministic capabilities, and available resources of the underlying technology domain. This information, which is obtained from the data plane, is exposed to the Path Computation to calculate the best route.

E2E Management Services

- **Time Synchronization Management:** E2E MS used to set up and maintain E2E time synchronization, providing information about the capabilities of PREDICT-6G system's time sync to other E2E services.
- **E2E Service Ingestion:** E2E MS designed to manage the E2E service requests received from operators, applications or external users, and forward it to the E2E Service Automation. This MS represents the entry point to the AICP.
- **E2E Service Automation:** E2E MS conceived to manage the E2E closed-loop service automation in all the underlying management domains. Apart from receiving requests from the E2E Service Ingestion, interacts with other modules like the E2E Path Computation or the E2E Resource Manager.

- **E2E Path Computation:** E2E MS used to calculate E2E routes and drive the path computation over technology-specific domains. To calculate the E2E path, it basically performs domain selection based on the multi-domain topology abstraction and, if the necessary information per domain is properly exposed (e.g., maximum latency supported by the domain), it selects the domain sequence that may potentially assure the service required KPIs. This module interacts with the E2E Service Automation as well as with E2E Topology Exposure MSs. If an external entity aimed to validate the feasibility of the E2E path is available (e.g., a Digital Twin), the E2E PC contacts it before sending the final path to the E2E Service Automation MS for configuration.
- **E2E Resource Manager:** E2E MS designed to request resource configuration in all the technology domains where a deterministic service must be provisioned. To perform this operation, this module interacts with the E2E Service Automation as well as with Resource Configurator MSs.
- **E2E Topology Exposure:** E2E MS conceived to expose topology information from the E2E perspective, i.e., abstracting topology information for all technology domains.
- **E2E Service Exposure:** E2E Management Service designed to expose service information from the E2E perspective to the user or the operator.

8 Operational Workflows

8.1 Summary of corresponding D3.1 content

This section describes the Operation Workflows, already proposed in Deliverable D3.1 [D3.1], updated accordingly with the last version of AICP architecture, described in Section 3, where the MSs corresponding to the DTs and AI/ML facility have been considered as external supporting systems.

8.2 E2E deterministic service provisioning

The figures below depict the E2E Deterministic Service Provisioning performed by exploiting AICP MSs only, while the usage of DTs and AI is described in dedicated subsections.

Figure 8-1 shows the first part of the workflow, focused on the E2E MD.

Figure 8-1: E2E Deterministic Service provisioning - E2E MD view.

- **Step 1.** User/Operator sends a Service Provisioning Request to the *E2E Service Ingestion MS*.
- **Step 2.** *E2E Service Ingestion* validates the format and the syntax of the Service Provisioning Request.
- **Step 3.** *E2E Service Ingestion* forwards the Service Provisioning Request to the *E2E Service Automation* for launching the provisioning process.
- **Step 4.** *E2E Service Automation* kicks off the provisioning process by requesting the cross-domain E2E path to the *E2E Path Computation*.
- **Step 5.** *E2E Path Computation* computes gross-grained E2E paths where the nodes in the network graph have the granularity of a domain, interconnected by the existing links between domain's border nodes.

- **Step 6.** *E2E Path Computation* starts an iterative path computation process in each local Management Domain by interacting with the corresponding technology-specific *Service Automation MS*. See details in **Figure 8-2**.
- **Step 7.** *E2E Path Computation* receives the local path selection from the different technology domains.
- **Step 8.** *E2E Path Computation* forwards the *E2E Path Computation* result to the *E2E Service Automation*.
- **Step 9.** *E2E Service Automation* triggers an iterative process for requesting the service provisioning in the corresponding domain through an interaction with the *Service Automation MS*. See details in **Figure 8-3**.
- **Step 10.** *E2E Service Automation* receives feedback about the local service provisioning from the *Service Automation MS*.
- **Step 11.** *E2E Service Automation* configures *E2E Monitoring* to collect from *Measurement Collection MSs* of each domain.
- **Step 12.** *E2E Service Automation* stores the E2E Service Information in the *E2E Service Exposure*.
- **Step 13.** *E2E Service Automation* informs about the *E2E Service Provisioning* to the *E2E Service Ingestion*.
- **Step 14.** *E2E Service Ingestion* informs the **user or the operator** about the success of the Service Provisioning Request.

Figure 8-2: E2E Deterministic Service provisioning – Loop 1, Local Path Computation view.

- **Steps 1 and 2.** *Service Automation MS* forwards the local path computation request to the local *Path Computation MS*.
- **Steps 3, 4 and 5.** *Path Computation MS* in each domain asks *Topology Exposure*, *Capability Exposure*, and *Resource Exposure* to retrieve information from domains.
- **Steps 6, 7, and 8.** *Topology Exposure*, *Capability Exposure*, and *Resource Exposure* get the corresponding information from the data plane, abstract it, and send it back to *Path Computation*.
- **Step 9.** *Path Computation* performs the local path calculation.
- **Step 10.** *Path Computation* forwards the selected path to the *Service Automation*
- **Step 11.** *Service Automation* forwards the local path selection to the E2E Path Computation.

Figure 8-3: E2E Deterministic Service provisioning – Loop 2, Local MD service provisioning view.

- **Step 1.** E2E Service Automation requests the service provisioning in the selected local domain through an interaction with the Service Automation MS.
- **Step 2.** Service Automation MS performs a request for resource configuration to the Resource Configuration MS.
- **Step 3.** Resource Configuration MS receives the request and configures resources directly on the data plane and provisions the path to the Service Automation MS.
- **Step 4.** Service Automation MS updates resource availability at the Resource Exposure MS.
- **Steps 5 and 6.** Service Automation MS configures the metrics to be collected
- **Step 7.** Service Automation MS informs the E2E Service Automation about the service provisioning in the local domain.

8.2.1 Resource configuration with DT and MLOps

This subsection details how DT and MLOps frameworks can be integrated as part of an E2E deterministic service provisioning workflow, in particular during the Resource Configuration stage performed when provisioning a specific MD service.

Figure 8-4: Resource Configuration workflow with Digital Twin and MLOps as part of E2E Service Provisioning.

As shown in **Figure 8-4**, during the MD Service Provisioning stage performed as part of the E2E Service provisioning, the Service Automation requests the Resource Configuration MS to allocate resources for a specific path previously selected (**Step 1**).

Resource Configuration MS can either run a proprietary resource configuration algorithm to allocate path resources or rely on an external resource allocation algorithm, which can be run and validated by an interaction between MD Digital Twin and MLOps frameworks. In the latter case (**Step 2**), the Resource Configuration MS can delegate the MD Digital Twin to allocate resources based on an internal logic (**Step 3**). Once the MD DT allocates resources and to evaluate the decision-making performed, the DT can contact the MLOps to run a specific AI-based algorithm that allows to predict the service KPI performance based on the resource allocation performed (**Step 4 and 5**). In this situation, the MLOps framework returns the AI-based inference to the Digital Twin, assessing Service KPIs (**Step 6**). If the result provided is satisfactory, the DT confirms the resource allocation and informs the Resource Configuration (**Step 7**) and the Service Automation (**Step 8**) about the configuration of the resources, i.e. service provisioning.

8.2.2 E2E Service Provisioning with DT

This workflow (depicted in **Figure 8-5** and **Figure 8-6**) reviews and extends the E2E Service Provisioning workflow assuming that the computation of the service also relies on digital twinning.

Figure 8-5: E2E Deterministic Service Provisioning assisted by DT.

In brief, different from the default workflow, upon the reception of a path request from the E2E Service Automation, the E2E Path Computation (E2E PC) selects a domain sequence able to support the requested connectivity. This selection is done over the multi-domain topology, which is composed from the collected topologies of the different local domains (steps 5 and 6 of **Figure 8-5**). If the E2E topology contains enriched information about the different local domains (e.g., maximum latency between borders), the E2E PC uses it to maximize the probability of selecting a domain sequence that provides a feasible E2E path. Afterwards, the E2E PC contacts each domain to request a local path computation (the inner loop, steps 7 and 8, from **Figure 8-5**, which is zoomed and detailed in **Figure 8-6**). Once the local paths of each domain have been computed and their KPIs have been estimated, they are returned to the E2E PC, which composes the E2E path and requests to the Digital Twin residing at the E2E level for E2E KPI estimation. If the estimation is inside the boundaries defined by the requirements of the request, the path is accepted, and the configuration phase is started (steps 11 to 17 in **Figure 8-5**).

Figure 8-6: Local Domain Path Computation assisted by DT.

As said, **Figure 8-6** details the path computation workflow that is followed at the Local Management Domain level. Once the Local Path Computation MS (PC) receives the request from the Service Automation, it computes the path according to the topology and capabilities available. Then, the PC requests the KPI estimation to the Digital Twin residing at the local domain. At this point, two options are considered for the validation of the estimated KPIs. If specific KPI requirements for the local domain have been defined at the E2E level, the validation process uses such values to decide whether the path is acceptable or not. On the contrary, if no specific KPI requirements have been defined at the E2E level for the domain, the E2E KPI requirements will be used for reference. If the path and KPI estimation are accepted at local domain level, both are sent back to the E2E Path Computation for final E2E path composition and KPI assessment (as depicted in **Figure 8-5**).

8.3 E2E deterministic service decommissioning

Figure 8-7 shows the first part of the E2E Deterministic Service decommissioning, focused on the E2E Management Domain.

Figure 8-7: E2E Deterministic Service decommissioning - E2E MD view.

- **Step 1.** User sends Service Decommissioning Request to *E2E Service Ingestion*.
- **Step 2.** *E2E Service Ingestion* forwards the request to *E2E Service Automation* where E2E service decommissioning is initiated.
- **Step 3.** *E2E Service Automation* retrieves additional service information from the *E2E Service Exposure* to perform the decommissioning.
- **Step 4.** *E2E Service Exposure* returns additional service information to the *E2E Service Automation*.
- **Step 5.** *E2E Service Automation* informs the *Service Automation MS* of the specific technology-domain about the service decommissioning and starts an iteration in the local MD. See **Figure 8-8** for the local MD loop.
- **Step 6.** *E2E Service Automation* is informed about the local service decommissioning and turns it into an E2E service decommissioning.
- **Step 7.** *E2E Service Automation* configures E2E monitoring to stop monitoring the parameters related to the decommissioned service.
- **Step 8.** *E2E Service Automation* removes the E2E service information from the *E2E Service Exposure MS*.

- **Step 9.** *E2E Service Automation* informs the *E2E Service Ingestion* about the E2E Service Decommissioning.
- **Step 10.** *E2E Service Ingestion* notifies the user or operator about the success of the E2E Service Decommissioning request.

Figure 8-8: E2E Deterministic Service provisioning – Local MD view.

- **Step 1.** *Service Automation MS* receives the local service decommissioning request.
- **Step 2.** *Service Automation MS* requests to the *Resource Configuration MS* the release of the resources allocated to the specific service in the local domain and the specific path.
- **Step 3.** *Resource Configuration MS* releases the corresponding resources.
- **Step 4.** *Service Automation MS* informs the *Resource Exposure MS* about the update on the resource availability.
- **Step 5.** *Service Automation MS* removes service information from the *Service Exposure*.
- **Step 6.** *Service Automation MS* requests to stop collecting monitoring parameters to the *Measurement Collection MS*.
- **Step 7.** *Service Automation MS* informs the *E2E Service Automation MS* about the local service decommissioning.

8.4 E2E deterministic service modification

This workflow is not affected by the AICP architectural updates as it consists of two different strategies based on compositions of provisioning and decommissioning workflows. In this sense the workflow is the same set of steps already reported in D1.2 [D1.2].

9 Standardisation of WP3 Innovations

During the lifetime of the project, WP3-related SDO contributions accounted for 22% of all contributions PREDICT-6G reported to the 6G-IA pre-standardization WG. **Table 9-1** provides the updated data for the Period January 2023 – 30 November 2024, which can be also found on the SNS JU page [SNS-JU-SDO, 2024].

Table 9-1: Contributions to Relevant Standardisation Bodies

Quarter	SDO	WG	Title
Q1 (Jan-Mar '23)	IETF	DetNet WG	DETNET multidomain extensions
Q2 (Apr-Jun '23)	ETSI	ISG MEC	MEC Application Package
Q3 (Jul-Sep '23)	ETSI	ISG MEC	MEC Application Package
Q4 (Oct-Dec '23)	IETF	PCE WG	Path Computation Based on Precision Availability Metrics
	ETSI	ISG MEC	MEC Application Package
	ETSI	ISG MEC	MEC Application Package

10 Conclusions

This document introduced solutions to enable deterministic communication services in next-generation networks by presenting significant developments in the AI-driven multi-stakeholder inter-domain control plane (AICP). Building on the foundational principles of interoperability and scalability, the work of WP3 has focused on addressing the complexities of managing and orchestrating deterministic services across heterogeneous and multi-technology domains.

The refined architectural design of AICP establishes a robust, modular framework capable of adapting to diverse operational scenarios, ensuring seamless integration and scalability. Through the incorporation of advanced technological enablers, such as AI/ML for intelligent resource allocation, Digital Twins for predictive modelling, and enhanced data collection mechanisms, the framework addresses critical requirements for real-time monitoring and performance optimization. Additionally, the inter-domain orchestration capabilities of AICP form the backbone for end-to-end deterministic service management, ensuring consistent performance across administrative and technological boundaries.

Operational methodologies and workflows have been detailed to provide a practical roadmap for implementing AICP in real-world scenarios. These workflows integrate architectural and technological innovations, offering clear guidance on service initialization, dynamic adaptation, and lifecycle management. The validation results and use cases presented demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed solutions, showcasing the potential of AICP to transform the delivery of deterministic communication services. By addressing the challenges of data-plane abstraction and multi-technology integration, Deliverable D3.3 thus provides a comprehensive approach to tackling the complexities of deterministic networking.

11 References

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